

The Relationship Between Social Media Addiction and Self-Esteem

To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 6-04, 2024, p. 01– 26. - 0099-0001-2404-0501.

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

1

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

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Article Application Date: 2024

Article Publication Date: 2024 Article Type: Compilation

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many objectives, including enhancing people' social networks, enabling the dissemination of information, and promoting personal self-expression. Nevertheless, these patterns of utilization entail certain hazards.

This article explores the correlation between addiction to social media and one's self-esteem. The rise in social media use is directly correlated with the escalation of social media addiction in people. Social media addiction is characterized by characteristics such as incessantly monitoring social media sites, perpetually devouring material, and forsaking other pursuits.

Abstract

Communication is an essential aspect of human existence, and with the progress of technology, the means of internet-based communication have undergone substantial transformations. Social media apps have played a significant role in this transformation and are used for

Self-esteem is a significant role in this particular circumstance. Engaging in social media may impact an individual's self-perception and perhaps result in a poor self-perception. Specifically, when people make

comparisons and aspire to idealized lives via social media, it may result in feelings of diminished self-esteem.

This essay will examine social psychology ideas and research in order to get insight into the correlation between addiction to social media and self-esteem. Furthermore,

recommended tactics to mitigate the psychological impacts of social media use will also be examined.

Keywords: Social Media Addiction, Self-Esteem, Relationship

INTRODUCTION

The correlation between social media addiction and people's self-esteem is being extensively studied due to the prevalent usage of social media. This review analyzes scholarly research investigating the impact of social media use on persons' self-esteem. Research in this topic is crucial for comprehending the psychological impacts linked to people's utilization of the internet and social media.

In the present day, due to the rapid advancement of technology, social media apps have emerged as crucial instruments that significantly influence individuals' modes of communication and ways of living. Social media is a platform where people exchange and engage with their emotions, ideas, information, and experiences (Przybylski et al., 2013). Nevertheless, this advancement in technology also prompts significant inquiries.

Social media addiction is a psychological state characterized by a compelling want to utilize these platforms, experience adverse feelings while abstaining from their usage, and a sense of relief when engaging with them (Hazar, 2011). Users often use social media programs extensively, devoting a substantial portion of their time to these sites. This might lead to unregulated social media use and have a detrimental impact on an individual's daily routine.

Self-esteem is the inclination of people to form favorable or unfavorable judgments about oneself (Aydın, 1996). It is crucial for individuals' psychological well-being that they have a

CURRENT SCIENCE

sense of adequacy, worth, and significance. Nevertheless, as social media use continues to rise, the impact it has on self-esteem is becoming more significant. Specifically, the act of comparing oneself to others and the portrayal of perfect lives on social media platforms may impact people's self-assessments and result in diminished self-worth.

This article will analyze the correlation between addiction to social media and one's self-esteem in the given setting. The focus will be on examining the impact of social media use on people's self-esteem and exploring strategies for effectively managing these impacts. The research is expected to enhance understanding of the psychological impacts of social media and aid users in using these platforms in a manner that promotes well-being.

AIM

The objective of this review is to methodically analyze the impact of social media use on self-esteem and consolidate the current research results. Gaining insight into the favorable or unfavorable impacts of social media use on self-worth might aid in the creation of psychological therapies and mitigate the potential hazards linked to people's engagement with social media.

METHOD

This research was conducted utilizing the compilation methodology. A comprehensive review of the current body of research on social media addiction and its impact on self-esteem was conducted, and the findings were synthesized and presented. This approach included the examination of pertinent research in the disciplines of social psychology, psychology, and communication. In addition, the viewpoints of specialists on the matter were also assessed. The essay seeks to provide a valuable tool for comprehending and safeguarding the mental well-being of those who use social media.

RESULTS

Recent study indicates that the usage of social media has multifaceted impacts on people' self-esteem. Several research indicate a correlation between excessive usage of social media and diminished self-esteem. Nevertheless, other studies suggest that social media might enhance interpersonal interactions and hence increase self-esteem. Furthermore, it is underscored that some elements, such as the kind of material, the intended purpose of usage, and the frequency of use, significantly influence this association.

Due to the rapid advancement of technology, the internet has emerged as a highly favored means of communication. Nevertheless, there are varying viewpoints about the communication possibilities facilitated by the internet. While proponents say that the internet's efficiency and speed provide beneficial outcomes, critics contend that it detrimentally affects social interactions and ensnares users in addictive behaviors (Ceyhan, 2008). Nevertheless, the unidirectional communication setting of conventional media has been transformed due to the internet's possibilities, enabling individuals to engage in reciprocal communication (Şeker, 2018).

Currently, social media is extensively used on the internet (Tektaş, 2014). As internet use grows, so does the number of social media services. Mobile access to social media apps results in a continuous growth in user numbers (Bulunmaz, 2018). Based on the statistics provided by Sirkhet Consultancy, digitalization and internet use in Turkey are seeing continuous growth. The estimate indicates that as of 2024, Turkey has 74.41 million internet users, accounting for 87.16 percent of the population. The number of social media users has surpassed 57 million. Currently, social media is extensively used on the internet (Tektaş, 2014). As internet use grows, so does the proliferation of social media services. Mobile access to social media apps results in a continuous growth in user numbers (Bulunmaz, 2018). Based on the statistics provided by Sirkhet Consultancy, digitalization and internet use in Turkey are seeing continuous growth. The estimate indicates that as of 2024, Turkey has 74.41 million internet users, accounting for 87.16 percent of the population. The current number of social media users exceeds 57 million according to Sirkhet Danışmanlık's projection for 2024. Social media refers to web-based apps

CURRENT SCIENCE

that use Web 2.0 technology, allowing users to access information and engage in communication with others (Gürsakar, 2009). Social media is a digital platform that enables individuals to discuss and articulate their thoughts and feelings (Tektaş, 2014). According to Kara and Coşkun (2012), social media, which is particularly favored by young individuals, enables users to engage with others and establish their own virtual environment.

The continuous updates of social media apps facilitate individuals in tasks such as job searching and content creation (Vural and Bat, 2010). Furthermore, the advent of social media has given rise to other resources, including collaborative projects, content communities, and virtual games. Social media facilitates self-awareness and communication, while also enabling content production (Kuss and Griffiths, 2017).

Nevertheless, it is crucial to acknowledge that social media serves not just as a means of facilitating the exchange of information and communication. Social media platforms facilitate interpersonal interaction, hence influencing the evolution of communication channels (Kaya et al., 2015). Social media facilitates the exchange of knowledge among professionals, leading to advancements in business practices. Additionally, it functions as a platform for individuals to share content with others (Hatipoğlu, 2009).

Within this particular framework, the proliferation of social media platforms leads to notable changes in both communication patterns and individuals' lifestyles. Nevertheless, more investigation is necessary to comprehend the impact of these alterations on mental well-being.

A study undertaken to assess the impact of social media use on mental well-being offers valuable insights into the intricate consequences of social media (Widyanto and Griffiths, 2006; Bergagna and Tartaglia, 2018). Hence, more investigation is required to get a more profound comprehension and effectively handle the impacts of social media use on mental well-being.

Due to the technical advancements of our day, social media has emerged as a quickly proliferating phenomena that occupies a central position in our daily existence. These digital platforms have become an essential component of our everyday lives and have a significant impact on several aspects of people's life (Köseoğlu and Al, 2013).

7

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Social media apps differ from conventional media in that they allow for regular updates and user-determined content (Bulunmaz, 2018). Several research in the literature have identified and documented the characteristics of social media platforms (Gürsakal, 2009; Güngör, 2013; Kınık, 2012).

Social media platforms facilitate communication and connect individuals from diverse geographical locations. These platforms foster user engagement and provide an environment that encourages active participation (Mayfield, 2010).

Social media programs are specifically developed to attract a broad range of users and are user-friendly. By eliminating barriers, the platform has become more accessible and user-friendly for all individuals (Mayfield, 2010).

Communities may be formed by individuals connecting with other users who have similar interests and hobbies via social media platforms. These communities foster a dynamic atmosphere of quick and efficient communication and exchange of knowledge (Mayfield, 2010).

Social media apps provide seamless transitions across several platforms and provide expedient access to material. By using this approach, users may efficiently and expeditiously get the desired information (Mayfield, 2010).

Social media platforms provide an egalitarian space that fosters uninhibited expression and encourages all users to openly share their opinions. This enhances the variety of the platform and fosters user collaboration (Mayfield, 2010).

Today, social media facilitates communication by providing users with the ability to access platforms at their convenience and from any location. This enhances the level of engagement and connection among individuals (Mayfield, 2010).

Research also yields crucial insights into comprehending the impact of social media use on people' self-esteem. A research done by Valkenburg, Peter, and Schouten (2006) found a substantial positive correlation between the self-esteem levels of teenagers and the favorable

CURRENT SCIENCE

comments they got on their self-presentation via social media accounts. This discovery illustrates the influence of social media on the formation of young individuals' self-perception.

Kararmak and Çetinkaya (2011) found that the locus of control of self-esteem influences emotions as cognitive elements. This discovery offers significant understanding into the impact of individuals' traumatic experiences on their self-esteem.

Eriş and İkizler (2013) discovered a detrimental correlation between self-esteem and levels of social anxiety in their research involving teenagers. This study determined that there is an inverse relationship between self-esteem and social anxiety, meaning that as self-esteem levels rise, social anxiety levels drop. Examining the correlation between young individuals' social media use and their degrees of social anxiety might provide valuable insights.

In Gürsoy's (2014) research, it was shown that self-esteem did not influence the attitudes of university students towards obtaining psychiatric assistance. This discovery highlights the significance of people' self-esteem levels when they seek psychological treatment in shaping their views towards such support.

Research investigating the correlation between social media use and self-esteem also garners interest. Şahin and Kumcağız (2017) discovered that university students with poor self-esteem had a greater prevalence of social media addiction. This discovery might enhance our comprehension of the potential impacts of social media use on one's self-esteem.

Sabırlı (2018) performed a research on university students and discovered no significant correlation between the frequency of smartphone use and self-esteem. This discovery illustrates the intricate nature of the impact of technology use on self-esteem and suggests the need for more research.

The research conducted by Sözkese and Biçer (2018) revealed that engaging in favorable self-presentations on Instagram had a detrimental impact on individuals' self-esteem. This discovery might enhance our comprehension of how social media sites can impact people' perception of their own identity.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Yüksel-Şahin and Öztoprak (2019) conducted a study which revealed that teenagers with poor self-esteem had elevated levels of social media addiction. This discovery illustrates the potential correlation between social media use and characteristics that might impact the self-esteem of young individuals.

Erbaş's (2019) research found a substantial correlation between ego resilience and problem-solving abilities and self-esteem. This discovery might enhance our comprehension of the potential correlation between self-esteem and individual aptitudes and cognitive functions.

In Derincegöz's (2019) study, a strong positive correlation was shown between self-esteem and forgiveness. This discovery emphasizes the impact of self-esteem on interpersonal interactions and emotional well-being.

Recent research undertaken in several countries has examined the impact of social media use on people's self-esteem. For instance, a research carried out in the United States found that self-esteem exhibited variations in response to the escalation of social media use among young individuals (Smith & Duggan, 2013).

A European research found that favorable self-presentations on social media platforms had a detrimental effect on self-esteem by promoting people's tendency to compare themselves with others (Vogel et al., 2014).

Research undertaken in Asia yields varying findings. An instance of this may be seen in a research done in South Korea, where it was discovered that the use of social media had a beneficial effect on one's self-esteem (Choi & Sung, 2018). Nevertheless, upon comprehensive evaluation, it becomes evident that social media use has multifaceted and varied impacts on self-esteem.

Conversely, comparable results were reported in research done in Africa. A study carried out in Nigeria revealed that the use of social media has an influence on the levels of self-esteem in young individuals, and an addiction to social media has an adverse effect on self-esteem (Adebayo & Olowu, 2019).

The commonality across these much research is the intricate and varied impact of social media use on self-esteem.

Social Media and Human Psychology

In modern times, as a result of the rapid progress of technology, social media has assumed a prominent position in people's lives. The internet has revolutionized how people communicate, share information, and interact via social media platforms. However, the widespread use of social media has also led to several negative consequences. This article will examine the psychological effects of using social media, specifically focusing on the addiction to social media and the subsequent consequences.

Social media platforms have a significant effect on individuals' daily lives. Advanced communication technologies facilitate cross-border connections. However, this ongoing involvement may potentially evolve into an addiction for some individuals. Kaya et al. (2015) defines social media addiction as the ongoing compulsion of users to often access platforms and encounter negative emotions.

Social media addiction is a kind of behavioral addiction that may result in many negative consequences. Baloğlu (2018) suggests that people may experience psychological and social harm as a consequence of using social media unintentionally. Devoting more time to social media platforms may specifically reduce individuals' in-person interactions and lead to social isolation.

The excessive usage of social media might have adverse effects on users' daily lives. According to Andreassen et al. (2012), those who are addicted to social media may experience a decrease in their social connections and a loss in their performance in academic or professional settings. Furthermore, the overuse of social media platforms may lead to detrimental physical health consequences and disrupt sleep patterns.

Psychosocial Effects of Social Media Addiction: Causes and Consequences

In contemporary times, the proliferation of social media platforms has brought about substantial changes in people's communication patterns and ways of life. The shift has resulted in a rise in the use of social media due to the impact of globalization and consumerism. Although social media provides users with the chance to interact, share their experiences, and express themselves, it also presents challenges such as addiction to social media.

The aspiration to reorganize one's life and alter the mode of communication is impactful in enhancing the use of social media. Individuals possess the chance to mold their own narratives via social media platforms and modify and disseminate the adversities they encounter. Nevertheless, this circumstance motivates individuals to strive for perfection and intensifies the burden of portraying oneself as they ought to in online settings.

Social media addiction stems from the appealing characteristics of social media platforms (Kırık, 2013; Hwang, 2017). The inclusion of features such as picture and video sharing, gaming, user interaction, music streaming, and messaging serve as attractive factors for users on social media platforms. These aspects' potential for improvement enables the identification of elements that enhance social media use and enhance its appeal to consumers (İliş, 2018).

Research has shown that individuals who are addicted to social media often utilize social media platforms often as a means of managing unpleasant emotions (Andreassen et al., 2012). According to Babacan (2016), addiction levels tend to rise particularly during times of stress, and social media fulfills psychological demands.

Social media platforms have an impact on the communication habits of persons with extroverted and introverted personality traits due to the shift in communication methods (Kraut et al., 2002). Extroverted persons may actively interact via social media, whereas introverted individuals find that social media platforms make communication easier (Tutgun - Ünal, 2015).

Individuals who are addicted to social media exhibit both physical and mental detriments, as noted by Griffiths in 1996. Individuals with addiction have a persistent need to often monitor

CURRENT SCIENCE

social media sites and get information. This condition has the potential to develop into an obsessive habit over a period of time and have a detrimental impact on individuals' actual life (Hwang, 2017).

Social media addiction is a significant issue in this context since it has a detrimental impact on the psychological well-being of people. Upon analyzing the origins and consequences of this addiction, it becomes evident that there are possible hazards that have the ability to detrimentally impact the lives of those who engage in it. Hence, it is crucial to use social media with mindfulness and restraint, and to promptly seek assistance from experts when signs of addiction become apparent.

Formation of Self-Concept and Social Interaction

Life is a voyage that encompasses an individual's introspective exploration and the revelations inside their inner realm. This expedition revolves on the fundamental question of personal identity: "Who am I?" The process of finding one's self-concept is initiated with a question.

The concept of self encompasses more than simply an identification certificate; it also involves exploring the profound aspects of one's inner being. This journey is the result of both internal experiences and interactions with the external environment.

Self-formation is influenced by a multifaceted interplay of several influences. The self-concept is shaped by an individual's experiences, talents, values, and connections. Moreover, apart from these fundamental components, the self-concept is also influenced by social conventions, cultural values, and the social environment.

The self undergoes development not just in terms of cognitive abilities, but also in emotional, social, and spiritual aspects. Interactions with others have a significant impact on an individual's perception of their own identity, causing it to evolve and transform. Hence, social contact plays a crucial part in the process of self-formation.

CURRENT SCIENCE

During an individual's introspective exploration, the self serves as a mirror of their internal realm and as a means to engage with the external environment. Hence, the self-concept provides a profound comprehension not only of one's own identity, but also of one's introspective journey and external connections.

The intricacy and adaptability of the self-concept have been extensively examined in the field of psychology. According to Derincegöz (2019), from the inception of humanity, the inquiry "who am I?" has been present. According to him, the endeavor to discover a solution to the topic enhances the significance of self-expression. Gander and Gardiner (2001) highlight the significance of the self-concept, particularly throughout adolescence and early adulthood. Koç (2008) asserts that social contacts have a significant impact on the formation of one's self-concept, since a person's views towards themselves are influenced by these encounters. Gerrig and Zimbardo (2014) define the self as a cognitive process that governs an individual's conduct towards themselves and others.

Self-Esteem: Definition, Development and Differences

An individual's self-esteem is molded by many forces encountered in their surroundings, beginning as early as the prenatal stage. Consequently, these influences shape the individual's self-perceptions and assessments. This process signifies a phase in which the person has the capacity to establish his own identity and establish connections with his surroundings.

Self-esteem is formed based on an individual's own positive or negative assessments of themselves. According to Branden (1994), a person's self-esteem is significantly influenced by their qualities, talents, and experiences.

High self-esteem refers to an individual's acceptance of oneself based on self-evaluations and being content with the self they have developed (Rosenberg, 1965).

CURRENT SCIENCE

Nevertheless, several variables influence one's self-esteem. According to Coopersmith (1967), elements such as achievement, values, desires, and defenses are crucial in shaping one's self-esteem. These variables may vary among individuals and impact their degree of self-esteem.

The amount of self-esteem is influenced by the disparities between an individual's seen self and their ideal self (Higgins, 1987). As the disparity increases, self-esteem tends to decrease. Rosenberg (1965) posited that possessing a favorable outlook towards oneself is indicative of elevated self-esteem, whilst harboring a pessimistic attitude may be indicative of diminished self-esteem.

Individuals who have low self-esteem often see themselves as being devoid of value or insufficient. This circumstance has the potential to undermine an individual's capacity to handle the challenges they face and have an adverse impact on their motivation (Baumeister et al., 1996).

Conversely, persons who possess high levels of self-esteem tend to be more proactive, optimistic, and successful in their interpersonal connections (Trzesniewski and Donnellan, 2010). These individuals possess self-awareness and often embrace their own value. This may facilitate the development of more robust interpersonal connections and enhance their ability to attain greater accomplishments in many aspects of their life.

Effects of Social Media Use on Self-Esteem

Currently, the migration of communication tools to virtual settings has facilitated the swift spread of information and ideas (Sözkesen and Biçer, 2018). Specifically, social media platforms have expanded the possibilities for users to express themselves and engage in social interactions (Çakmak, 2012). Social media platforms provide individuals with the opportunity to identify themselves and showcase their identities in many ways (Ünlü- Dalaylı, 2018).

Nevertheless, social media platforms provide functionalities that might impact people' self-esteem. For instance, variables such as the quantity of likes and the quantity of followers have

CURRENT SCIENCE

a role in people' development of their self-esteem (Aladwani and Almarzouq, 2016). Engaging in this activity may foster the development of a healthy sense of self-worth and enhance the capacity to effectively manage adverse emotions (Mann, 2004).

Nevertheless, it is not without its drawbacks, one of which being the issue of social media addiction. Research conducted by Şahin and Kumcağız (2017) has shown a correlation between excessive use of social media and a decrease in self-esteem. This condition may prompt people to seek validation for their perceived lack of importance in their everyday life by turning to social media (Josephs, Bosson, & Jacobs, 2003).

Individuals with low self-esteem may have difficulties in their regular communication and social interactions, particularly. Nevertheless, social media platforms provide a means for these people to have a greater sense of ease when it comes to discussing and expressing their thoughts and feelings (Leary and Macdonald, 2003).

Variables that influence self-esteem may likewise impact the propensity for social media addiction. For instance, in order to make up for the lack of likes, people may portray an altered version of themselves on social media (Tutgun-Ünal, 2015). Specific demographic cohorts, such as college students, are especially impacted by the practice of forming contacts via social media (Kırcaburun, 2016).

Self-Esteem and Social Media Addiction: A New Perspective

The proliferation of social media platforms has led to a shift in people's online behavior (Sezer, 2013). Recent study indicates that the use of the internet, particularly social media, might lead to the emergence of new issues instead of alleviating negative feelings in people (Whang, Lee, & Chang, 2003; Tsai & Lin, 2003; Esgin et al., 2012).

Specifically, research has shown that there is a favorable correlation between the number of likes teenagers get on social media and their overall well-being (Yahyagil, 2017). Young

CURRENT SCIENCE

individuals use social media platforms as a means of self-expression and to enhance their self-worth, as shown by Ong (2013).

Nevertheless, the detrimental consequences of using social media cannot be disregarded. Specifically, the need to often monitor the quantity of likes and follows might undermine people's interpersonal connections in the physical world (Tokunaga, 2016). This may result in a condition known as social media addiction (Kuss and Griffiths, 2017).

Excessive use of social media may have detrimental effects on people's mental well-being (Andreassen, Pallesen, & Griffiths, 2017). Specifically, persons with diminished self-esteem are more prone to developing an addiction to social media (Koc, Gürbüz, & Çetinkaya, 2018). This scenario has the potential to heighten people's reliance on social media if they experience a sense of insignificance (Liu and Baumeister, 2005).

Social Media Addiction and Self-Esteem: Social Psychological Approach

Social media addiction refers to the excessive and unregulated use of social media platforms by people. These impacts may be substantial, particularly on one's self-esteem, resulting in psychological and societal consequences. Social psychology theories provide a crucial foundation for comprehending the connection between addiction to social media and one's self-esteem.

Social Comparison Theory: The social comparison hypothesis posits that people engage in comparisons with others, which subsequently influence their self-assessments. Specifically, evaluations made using metrics like as likes, follows, and shared material may have a detrimental impact on people's self-worth. (Festinger, 1954)

CURRENT SCIENCE

Self-Perception Theory: Self-perception theory posits that people develop a view of their own talents, skills, and values. Social media addiction may lead to persons excessively relying on input from social media platforms to shape their self-perception. In this scenario, receiving favorable responses on social media enhances one's self-esteem, whilst receiving unfavorable responses might have a detrimental impact on self-esteem. The source cited is Rosenberg's work from 1965.

Social Connections Theory: The notion of social connections highlights the impact of social ties on an individual's mental health and sense of self-worth. Hence, over reliance on social media might result in less face-to-face social engagements, thereby leading to a decline in self-esteem. The reference used is Baumeister and Leary (1995).

Conclusion, Discussion and Recommendations

This study examines the correlation between social media addiction and people' self-esteem, drawing upon social psychology theories and existing research in this area. The evidence we have gathered confirms that the usage of social media has a substantial impact on an individual's self-esteem.

Past study in the literature indicates that people' self-esteem might be adversely impacted by excessive and uncontrolled usage of social media. The relationship may be well explained by social psychology theories such as social comparison theory, self-perception theory, and social connections theory.

Based on these results, some techniques may be suggested to mitigate the psychological impacts of social media usage:

CURRENT SCIENCE

Intentional Usage: It is advisable to promote the deliberate and regulated usage of social media platforms by individuals. One may apply strategies such as setting time restrictions on daily social media usage or restricting usage during certain time periods for particular activities.

Encouraging individuals to prioritize and allocate more time to engage in face-to-face social contacts and participate in real-life activities is beneficial. Engaging in activities such as direct interpersonal conversation, personal interests, and physical activities may enhance people's social connections and boost their self-worth.

Engaging in a digital detox, which involves abstaining from social media for certain durations, may effectively mitigate social media addiction and enable people to prioritize self-care.

Psychological help and counseling services should be offered to people to address issues related to social media addiction and low self-esteem. These programs may assist persons in comprehending their emotional requirements and cultivating effective coping strategies.

These guidelines outline measures and safeguards that may be used to mitigate the psychological impacts of social media usage. Nevertheless, given the intricate and varied nature of social media, it is crucial to customize these techniques according to people's own requirements and inclinations in order to achieve desired outcomes.

NOTIFICATIONS

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external consultants.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declared no conflict of interest regarding this article.

Financial Support: The authors reported no use of financial support related to this article.

Limits and Limitations

19

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This review presented findings compiled from various studies to examine the impact of social media use on individuals' self-esteem. However, this review has some limits and limitations.

First, the review faces a limitation arising from the methodological diversity of the studies reviewed. The studies reviewed used different sample sizes, measurement tools and analysis methods. This may affect the comparability and generalizability of the findings .

Second, the review is limited to the sources accessible during the literature review. Therefore, it is possible that some important studies were overlooked. Future reviews should address this limitation by drawing on a broader literature base.

Third, the rapidly changing nature of social media platforms may limit the timeliness of the collection. This review is based on research conducted over a specific period of time and does not include new developments that have emerged subsequently.

Finally, the review may not fully capture the complexity of social media use. There are many factors that affect the effects of social media use on individuals, and this review may not be able to cover all these factors.

These limits and limitations should be taken into account in interpreting and applying the findings of the review. Future research may better understand the psychological effects of social media use by examining this area in more depth and addressing these limitations.

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